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**PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF NAUCLEA ORIENTALIS AS
A POTENTIAL MEDICINAL PLANT – BRIDGING TRADITIONAL
REMEDIES WITH MODERN CLINICAL NEEDS**

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ABSTRACT

The global rise in healthcare expenditure and the adverse effects of synthetic drugs pose significant threats to the health sector. This has led to a growing demand for potent, innovative herbal remedies from medicinal plants to address these health concerns. *Nauclea orientalis* is a medicinal plant extensively used in traditional medicine since ancient times for its therapeutic properties. This study evaluates the antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of the methanolic extracts of *Nauclea orientalis* and provides experimental evidence for its potential traditional and modern clinical use. A free radical scavenging assay, with concentrations ranging from 150-400 µg/ml, was used to assess the antioxidant capacity of methanolic extracts from leaves and roots of *Nauclea orientalis*. According to the results, the highest percentage of inhibition (%) resulted at the 400 µg/ml concentration, showing $75.10 \pm 0.09\%$ for leaves and $73.38 \pm 0.09\%$ for roots, respectively, in which the leaves extract showed higher potential than roots extract. The antimicrobial susceptibility test was adopted to measure the potency of the extracts to be used as antimicrobial agents against common pathogens. Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* (ATCC® 25922™), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC® 27853™), and gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC® 29213™) were used as the test microorganisms. Among the methanolic leaves and root extracts, the leaves extract exhibited the highest antimicrobial activity with diameters of inhibition zones measuring 12.67 ± 0.58 mm, 10.00 ± 2.65 mm, and 10.00 ± 1.00 mm against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa*, respectively. Hence, this study confirms that *Nauclea orientalis* possesses potent medicinal properties that can be modified and further developed to serve as a potent antioxidant or in antimicrobial therapy.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, antioxidant, ethnopharmacology, natural products, medicinal properties

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